

A method for efficient multiplication of dense matrix using an approach of parallel and recursive computing*

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Abstract— In this paper we describe a computational model oriented to the efficient processing of dense matrices using a parallel and linear recursive synchronous computing approach. The architecture, design, and performance of this conceptual model are described; it is denominated the Parallel and Recursive Computing Model or PRCM. This model has been used to address the problem of function list evaluation. The model is based on important computational notions such as parallelism and recursion theory, which govern both its organization and operation mode. Fine-grain parallelism is exploited by means of synchronous processing across processor pipelines; concurrency and execution control are achieved via dataflow. The structure of the PRCM is organized as a stack of recursive levels that control the massive processing of dense matrices as a large list of linear recursive functions.

Keywords— Computing model, Matrix multiplication algorithm, Parallel recursive computing, Linear recursive function, Pipeline, Dataflow.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we describe a computational model oriented to the efficient processing of dense matrices using a parallel and linear

recursive synchronous computing approach. The architecture, design, and performance of this conceptual model are described; it is denominated the Parallel and Recursive Computing Model or PRCM. This model has been motivated by studies made in [1,2,3,4], which address the problem of function list evaluation. The model is based on important computational notions such as parallelism and recursion theory, which govern both its organization and operation mode. Fine-grain parallelism is exploited by means of synchronous processing across processor pipelines; concurrency and execution control are achieved via dataflow. The structure of the PRCM is organized as a stack of recursive levels that control the massive processing of dense matrices as a large list of linear recursive functions.

The problem of matrix multiplication is to compute the product C of two matrices as shown in Fig. 1. Let A be an $m \times n$ matrix, B an $n \times k$ matrix, and the result C an $m \times k$ matrix. An equation to compute the product is $C = A_1B_1 + A_2B_2 + \dots + A_nB_n$ where A_i and B_i are the i -th column of A and the i -th row of B , respectively, and the product A_iB_i denotes an outer product. Therefore, the matrix multiplication can be carried out in n recursions (each executes an outer product A_kB_k):

$$c_{ij}^{(k)} = c_{ij}^{(k-1)} + a_{ik} * b_{kj} \quad \text{for } i, j, k = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

This recurrence equation leads to a recursive

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expression. Computing c_{ij} resembles the multiplication of the elements from row i of A by the elements of column j of B , summed.

$$(a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{in}) \begin{pmatrix} b_{1j} \\ b_{2j} \\ \vdots \\ b_{nj} \end{pmatrix} = c_{ij}, \text{ where}$$

$$c_{ij} = a_{i1}b_{1j} + a_{i2}b_{2j} + \dots + a_{in}b_{nj} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{ik}b_{kj}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & \dots & b_{1n} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & \dots & b_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ b_{n1} & b_{n2} & \dots & b_{nn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & \dots & c_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & \dots & c_{nn} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$c_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{ik}b_{kj}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Fig. 1: General manner of matrix multiplication: Vector–Vector and Matrix–Matrix product.

Then, the problem becomes a chain of requirements such as $\{R_1 : \text{Mult-MV}(A, b_1), R_2 : \text{Mult-MV}(A, b_2), \dots, R_k : \text{Mult-MV}(A, b_k)\}$, which implies a queue of recursive tasks that the PRCM can process.

Those matrix operators can be systematically decomposed into large numbers of parallel recursive computations. For example, an $N \times N$ matrix product can be decomposed into N^2 dot products, N^3 scalar multiplications and additions, etc. Using pipelining [6], we can apply a chaining treatment to a recursive function F_r by decomposing it into recursive stages $(F_{r1}, F_{r2}, \dots, F_{rn})$, each of which can be executed

independently. In this way, a pipeline is configured to support the simultaneous processing of a chain of recursive stages. Since each recursive stage F_i can be evaluated in a fraction T/n of the total time T of F (assuming all stages take the same time), and the overlapping introduced by pipelining allows n tasks to be completed in time T . Using the “divide and conquer” paradigm, we can define matrix multiplication recursively.

II. DEFINITIONS AND PRELIMINARIES

A model of computation is a formal, abstract definition of a computer. Using a model, one can more easily analyze the intrinsic execution time or memory space of an algorithm while ignoring many implementation details. Many models of computation exist, differing in computing power (i.e., some models can perform computations that are impossible for others) and in the cost of various operations.

Recursion, pipelining, and dataflow are very powerful computation models often used to solve problems with implicit and explicit parallelism. Individually, each model is powerful, but their combination can improve their scope.

1. Recursive Computations

Recursive computation is a model based on Recursive Functions Theory [5], which, like Turing Machine theory, provides a way to formalize the intuitive notion of an effective method. It identifies the same class of functions as those that are Turing-computable, lending support to Church’s Thesis. Recursive computations can also be seen as recursive algorithms or functions that are defined in terms of themselves: to accomplish a task, a function calls itself with a part of the task. Recursion is the concept of well-defined self-reference. For example, the factorial of a positive integer N is defined as $N! = N \cdot (N - 1)!$ with $0! = 1$.

2. Pipelining

Pipelining is a form of embedding parallelism or concurrency in a computer system. It refers to the segmentation of a computational process into several subprocesses, each executed by dedicated autonomous units. Thus, pipelining can be defined as the technique of decomposing a repeated sequential process into subprocesses, each of which can be executed efficiently on a special dedicated autonomous module that operates overlapped or concurrently with the others [6]. Pipelining can be exploited at different levels: data, instructions, or tasks.

Using pipelining, a recursive function F_r can be decomposed into recursive stages $(F_{r1}, F_{r2}, \dots, F_{rn})$ that can be executed independently. A pipeline is then configured to support the simultaneous processing of a chain of recursive stages. If each stage F_i takes a fraction T/n of the total time T of F , the overlapping allows n tasks to be completed in time T .

3. Dataflow Model

The dataflow model is an alternative to the stored-program (von Neumann) execution model. Because it relies on a graph representation of programs, its strengths complement those of the stored-program model. The fundamental principles of dataflow were developed by Jack Dennis [7] in the early 1970s. The dataflow model avoids two features of the von Neumann model that become bottlenecks in exploiting parallelism: the program counter and the global updatable store. The computational rule, also known as the firing rule, specifies the condition for instruction execution: an instruction is executable when all its input operands are available. The effect of firing an instruction is the consumption of its input values and the generation of output values. Consequently, the model is asynchronous and self-scheduling; instruction sequencing is constrained only by data dependencies. A dataflow

program can be represented as a directed graph whose nodes represent instructions and arcs represent data dependencies. Data values propagate along arcs as tokens. In a dataflow architecture, program execution involves receiving, processing, and sending tokens that contain data and a tag. Dependencies between data are resolved through tag matching and transformation. The matching and execution units are connected by an asynchronous pipeline, with queues to smooth load variations.

III. THE PRCM COMPUTATION MODEL

The computation model proposed in this work is used for the large-scale parallel processing of lists of linear recursive functions. It describes a computing approach oriented to the efficient processing of dense matrices using parallel and linear recursive techniques. This model has been motivated by studies made in [1,2,3,4], which deal with the problem of function list evaluation. Thus, this paper proposes a computer architecture that exploits fine-grained parallel processing across pipelining, dataflow, and recursion. The model is called the Parallel-Recursive Computing Model (PRCM). The PRCM is conceived as a specialized numeric processor connected to a front-end computer.

The essential components of the model are: the dense matrices A and B to be multiplied, expressed as a list of linear recursive functions; two pipelines of processor arrays with their data memories; a message-passing mechanism for communication among processors; and a set of elementary operators (basic instruction set).

The features of the PRCM architecture (shown in Fig. 2) are as follows:

- 1) Each recursive level of the PRCM is identical and contains one downward processor and one upward processor, both connected to a two-port local memory. Thus, the PRCM

has a static topology based on a stack of recursive levels.

- 2) From another perspective, two pipeline processors form the PRCM stack: one downward pipeline and one upward pipeline.
- 3) A Memory Control Unit handles address assignment and deallocation.
- 4) Synchronization is based on a message-passing mechanism between processors.
- 5) A list or queue of linear recursive functions to be evaluated.
- 6) An elemental instruction set.

- $Q_{in} = \{f(x_1), f(x_2), \dots, f(x_n)\}$ is the input list of functions to be evaluated recursively in parallel.
- $Q_{out} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$ is the output list of results.
- $L = (PD_i, LM_i, PU_i)$ is a recursive level, with PD_i the downward processor, PU_i the upward processor, both connected to a private two-port local memory LM_i .
- $PD_i = (Ch_{in}, Ch_{out}, Ch_{int}, Is)$ where Ch_{in} connects to PD_{i-1} , Ch_{out} connects to PD_{i+1} , Ch_{int} connects PD_i with PU_i in the same level. $Is = (I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n)$ is the common instruction set.

Fig. 2: PRCM recursive multilevel structure.

Formally, the PRCM can be represented by a tuple (Q_{in}, Ch, L, Q_{out}) where:

The first level (PD_0, PU_0) is the input/output interface with the host. There exist two pipelines: one downward $(PD_0, PD_1, \dots, PD_{n-1})$ and one upward (PU_{n-1}, \dots, PU_0) , which together overlap matrix processing through recursive pipelining and concurrency.

Communication in the PRCM is simple: messages are passed across channels. A message has the format $\langle \text{function, argument, address} \rangle$, where the argument is a number (e.g., recursion depth) and the address is assigned by the memory controller.

IV. PRCM OPERATION MODE

This section demonstrates how the PRCM works using the factorial function as an example of a linear recursive function. The PRCM operates on three principles: a recursive model framework, processor activation according to the dataflow model, pipeline functionality, and message passing as the communication paradigm.

The process of evaluating a factorial function using the PRCM is illustrated in Fig. 3 and proceeds as follows:

- 1) PD_0 receives an argument (e.g., $X = 4$) from the host and stores it at an address assigned by the memory controller.

Fig. 3: A simple example of factorial function processing using the PRCM.

- 2) PD_0 decrements the data and sends a message downward to PD_1 .
- 3) Each downward processor repeats this step until the data becomes 1 (the recursion stop condition).
- 4) When a processor decrements the data to 1, it sends a message to the upward processor in the same level (e.g., PU_3).
- 5) The upward processor receives the message, retrieves the argument, multiplies it with the content of its local memory, and sends the result upward.
- 6) Each upward processor repeats this step until the message reaches PU_0 .
- 7) PU_0 returns the final result to the host and frees the memory address.

When a processor becomes free, it can receive a new argument from the host, generating a continuous flow through both pipelines.

1. Matrix Multiplication Using the PRCM

Matrix computation is usually considered a topic in linear algebra or numerical analysis. Using the “divide and conquer” approach, we can define matrix multiplication recursively.

The elements of a matrix have a relative position: A_{ij} is the element in the i -th row and j -th column of A . Matrix operators can be systematically decomposed into large numbers of parallel recursive computations using position indices. For example, an $N \times N$ matrix product can be decomposed into N^2 dot products, N^3 scalar multiplications, and additions. This allows a chaining treatment similar to a recursive function F_r decomposed into stages $(F_{r,1}, F_{r,2}, \dots, F_{r,n})$, each executed independently via pipelining. Thus, the problem exhibits recursive behavior and can be processed by the PRCM.

Before processing, a copy of matrix A is stored in the local memory of every PRCM level, and the i -th column of matrix B (a column vector) is stored in the i -th level. This generates a chain (pipeline) where each element has two indices: its position in matrix A and the index j in the vector B_j . The index j indicates the depth (level) where one element of the result matrix C is produced.

V. PRCM MODEL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Performance analysis studies execution times. The execution time is the time elapsed between the instant when all nodes begin execution and the instant when the last node terminates. Performance analysis determines the range of problem sizes and feasible applications. Performance models are not a substitute for computational experiments but are used to gain qualitative insight.

The time complexity of an algorithm is the amount of time (or number of operations) needed to complete the task. An upper bound is provided by any algorithm, but lower bounds are generally hard to obtain. We measure the PRCM's performance by counting the operations executed during matrix multiplication.

1. Storage Complexity

The memory model has a centralized control. It requires more address space for each level $i = 2, \dots, n$ where n is the PRCM depth. The memory needed per level is $2 \times n$. Thus, if D is the depth of the PRCM and m is the number of memory words per level, then

$$m = 2D^2.$$

2. Time Complexity

The execution time to evaluate one recursive function (task) includes the processing time plus the waiting delay before execution begins:

$$\text{Time of first task } S_1 = a_1(t_b + t_s)$$

$$\text{Time of second task } S_2 = S_1 + a_2(t_b + t_s)$$

⋮

$$\text{Time of } k\text{-th task } S_k = S_{k-1} + a_k(t_b + t_s)$$

where k is the length of the list of recursive functions, a_k is the argument of the k -th task, t_b is the downward propagation time, t_s is the upward propagation time, and S_{k-1} is the time of the $(k-1)$ -th task.

The total sequential time from the start of the first task to the completion of the last task is:

$$T_{\text{SEQ}} = S_k = (t_b + t_s) \sum_{i=1}^k a_i \quad (1)$$

3. PRCM Workload Sorting

Two cases are of interest:

a) *Descending order:*

$a_i > a_{i+1}$ for $i = 1, \dots, k-1$. Then the time for the first task is $a_1(t_b + t_s)$. For k tasks:

$$T_{\text{PRCM}} = a_1(t_b + t_s)$$

and the acceleration A_c is

$$A_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k a_i(t_b + t_s)}{a_1(t_b + t_s)} = 1 + \frac{\sum_{i=2}^k a_i}{a_1} \quad (3)$$

Here $A_c > 1$ when $k > 1$ (and $A_c = 1$ if $k = 1$). No collisions occur, yielding the best performance.

b) *Ascending order:*

$a_i \leq a_{i+1}$ for $i = 1, \dots, k-1$. Then

$$T_{\text{PRCM}} = (k-1)t_b + a_k(t_b + t_s) \quad (4)$$

The acceleration is

$$\begin{aligned} A_c &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k a_i(t_b + t_s)}{(k-1)t_b + a_k(t_b + t_s)} \\ &= 1 + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} a_i(t_b + t_s) - (k-1)t_b}{(k-1)t_b + a_k(t_b + t_s)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Again $A_c > 1$ for $k > 1$. However, collisions may occur when tasks flow upward, potentially limiting performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Processing a large list of matrix multiplication tasks in descending order yields the best performance of the PRCM model without collisions. Fine-grain processing of dense matrix multiplication requires intensive numerical calculations. These demands call for a hardwired chip based on the PRCM model, integrating many processing elements. By means of recursivity and concurrency, it is possible to improve performance for problems that exhibit recursive behavior. The PRCM model is conceived as a specialized numeric processor connected to a front-end computer.

A major objective of the PRCM model is to develop a complete and consistent low-level execution model that establishes the operational relationship between the parallel programming model described above and hardware mechanisms that could be supported by a chip implemented using VLSI technology or reconfigurable logic systems such as FPGAs.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Amimaya, M. Takesue, R. Hasegawa, and H. Mikami, "Implementation and evaluation of a list-processing-oriented data flow machine," in *Proc. 13th Annual Int. Symp. Computer Architecture*, IEEE, 1986, pp. 10–18.
- [2] E. Albacea, "Computation list evaluation and its applications," *Parallel Processing Letters*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 321–329, Dec. 1992.
- [3] C. Wedler and C. Lengauer, "On linear list recursion in parallel," *Acta Informatica*, vol. 35, pp. 875–909, Springer-Verlag, 1998.
- [4] C. Acosta, R. Surós, and E. Montagne, "Un modelo computacional para el procesamiento de listas de funciones recursivas lineales," in *XXVI Conferencias Latinoamericanas de Informatica (CLEI'2000)*, Mexico, Sept. 2000.
- [5] W. H. Burge, *Recursive Programming Techniques*. The Systems Programming Series, Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA, 1975.
- [6] C. V. Ramamoorthy and H. F. Li, "Pipeline architecture," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 61–102, Mar. 1977.
- [7] J. B. Dennis, "Dataflow computation: A case study," in *Computer Architecture – Concepts and Systems*, V. M. Milutinovic, Ed., North-Holland, 1988, pp. 354–404.